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**Effective Contact Tracing as a Means of Mitigating Community Transmission of Covid-19
among Exposed Persons in Developing Countries**

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Abstract

Contact tracing is one of the public health interventions used to combat community spread of communicable diseases, by tracing and encouraging contacts of persons who have been diagnosed with an infectious disease in order to examine and treat anyone who has contacted the disease or quarantine those who had contact but do not show signs and symptoms of the disease. This paper reviews strategies to achieving effective contact tracing as a means of militating community spread of COVID-19 in developing countries. Contact tracing involves a systematic approach beginning with the identification of the index case, defining the effective contact, determining the time frame during which new infection would have occurred, interviewing the index case, locating effective contacts, isolate or quarantine and analyzing contact tracings and contacts' network. In developing countries, this procedure is however impeded by some challenges such as difficulty in locating contact persons, contact persons' unwillingness to provide reliable information, stigmatization of infected persons, insufficient follow-up of contacts, managing contact tracing personnel, inadequate manpower, community misperception regarding COVID-19 and poorly equipped treatment centers. To overcome these challenges, effective health education and sensitization, efficient management of contact tracing personnel, proper mapping, naming of streets and house numbering and improving manpower status will pave way for effective contact tracing as a means of mitigating community spread of COVID-19.

Keywords: Contact tracing, mitigation, community-transmission, COVID-19, developing-countries.